

Study on the spectral characteristics of 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzoic acid in different pH and α -cyclodextrin

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Abstract : Effect of buffer solutions of different pH and α -cyclodextrin (α -CD) on the absorption and fluorescence spectra of 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzoic acid (vanillic acid HMB) have been investigated. The inclusion complex of α -CD with HMB is investigated by UV-Visible and fluorimetry and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) methods. These studies show that HMB forms 1 : 1 inclusion complex with α -CD. There is an unusual blue shift of hydroxyl ion (dianion) in the α -CD medium. This confirms that the -OH group is present in the interior part of the α -CD cavity and -COOH group is present in the upper part of the α -CD cavity. A mechanism is proposed to explain the inclusion process.

Keywords : 4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy benzoic acid (vanillic acid HMB), α -cyclodextrin (α -CD), pH effect, inclusion complex.

Introduction

The spectral characteristics (absorption and fluorescence spectra and their intensities) of an aromatic molecule are dependent on the nature as well as on the position of the substituent in the aromatic ring¹. Therefore, the fluorescence and absorption spectra of an aromatic molecule may differ significantly from isomer to isomer²⁻⁴. In monofunctional molecules, electron withdrawing groups like carboxylic acids, aldehydes, esters, tertiary nitrogen or cyano groups become more basic in the excited singlet state and thus lead to a red shift in the spectra, if π - π^* is the lowest energy transition. Similarly electron donating groups such as hydroxy and amine become stronger acids in the S_1 state and lead to a red shift or a blue shift in the electronic spectra, when these molecules get deprotonated or protonated respectively. In bi-functional molecules having electron donating and electron withdrawing functional groups, the spectral characteristics of individual groups are retained, i.e. spectral behaviour remains qualitatively the same in the ground and the excited states. There are certain molecules that contain the above kind of functional groups where the excited state reactions are quite different from those in the ground state⁵⁻⁷.

Recently pH and β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) dependences of the photophysical properties of different molecules have been studied. In this paper we are reporting the effects of

pH and α -CD on spectral characteristics of 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzoic acid.

Experimental

Absorption spectral measurements were carried out with a Hitachi Model U-2001 UV-Vis spectrophotometer, and fluorescence measurements were made using a Jasco FP-550 spectrofluorimeter. The pH values in the range 1-7 were measured on Elico pH meter model LI-10T.

HMB and α -CD were obtained from E. Merck and recrystallized from aqueous ethanol⁸. The purity of the compound was checked by similar fluorescence spectra when excited with radiations of different wavelengths. All solvents used were of the highest grade (spectrograde or AnalaR) commercially available. Triply distilled water was used for the preparation of aqueous solutions. pH ~ 1 was made by mixing H₂SO₄-H₂O mixture. The solutions were prepared just before taking the measurements.

α -Cyclodextrin solution preparation :

The concentration of stock solution of HMB (2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) was transferred into 10 ml volumetric flasks containing 0.2 ml of this solution followed by the addition of 0, 0.002, 0.004, 0.006, 0.008, 0.01 mol dm⁻³ α -CD solutions into volumetric flasks. The mixed solution was diluted to 10 ml with triply distilled water (or) appropriate buffer solution and shaken thoroughly. The absorption and fluorescence spectra were recorded and

intensities were measured at 30 ± 1 °C using 1 cm quartz cell.

Preparation of solid complex of HMB with α -CD : Accurately weighed 1.2 g α -CD was placed into 50 ml conical flask and 30 ml distilled water was added and the solution was oscillated enough. After that, 0.2 g HMB was put into a 200 ml beaker and 20 ml distilled water was added and put over electromagnetic stirrer to stir until it was dissolved. Then α -CD solution was slowly poured into HMB solution and the solution was continuously stirred for 48 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was put into refrigerator for 48 h. At this time we observed that a white powder was precipitated out. The precipitate was filtered by G4 sand filter funnel. Free α -CD and HMB was washed with deionized water and methanol. After that the white solid inclusion complex was dried for 12 h in hot oven at 60 °C. The yield was 60%.

Results and discussion

α -Cyclodextrin effects :

Table 1 and Figs. 1A-D show that absorption and

fluorescence spectra of HMB in pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7 solutions containing various concentrations of α -CD. In pH \sim 7 HMB exists as an anion. It is well known fact that, deprotonation of -COOH group gives blue shifted maxima^{9,10}. Hence we also recorded spectrum at pH \sim 1. The absorption maxima of HMB in pH \sim 1 appears at 292, 291, 290, 289 nm, whereas in pH \sim 7 the maxima appears at 285, 285.60, 286 nm. Upon increasing the concentration of α -CD in pH \sim 1, the absorption maxima is blue shifted from 292 nm to 290 ± 2 nm. But at pH \sim 7, it is slightly red shifted from 285 nm to 285.40, 285.60, 286 nm. However, the absorption intensities of both solutions are regularly increased with increasing concentration of α -CD. The spectral of HMB in both solutions are similar to each other.

The effect of α -CD on the fluorescence spectra of HMB is more pronounced than the corresponding effect on the absorption spectra. In emission spectra it is blue shifted in pH \sim 1 (354–348 nm). Whereas in pH \sim 7, there is no observable change, but it is slightly

Table 1. Absorption and fluorescence maxima (nm) of HMB at different concentration of α -CD

Sl. no.	Concentration of $[\alpha\text{-CD}]$	pH \sim 7			pH \sim 1		
		λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}
1.	0 (without α -CD)	285	3.62	325.4	292	3.74	354
2.	0.002	285.40	3.70	325.6	291.80	3.86	349
3.	0.004	285.80	3.70	326.8	290.80	3.80	350
4.	0.006	285.60	3.65	326.6	290.20	3.87	349
5.	0.008	285.60	3.65	326.8	289.80	3.79	348
6.	0.01	286	3.72	326.6	289.80	3.87	348
K (1 : 1) M^{-1}	–	375	–	398	209	–	236

Fig. 1A. Absorption spectra of HMB in different α -CD concentration at pH \sim 7.

Fig. 1B. Absorption spectra of HMB in different α -CD concentration at pH \sim 1.

Fig. 1C. Fluorescence spectra of HMB in different α -CD concentration at pH ~ 7 .

Fig. 1D. Fluorescence spectra of HMB in different α -CD concentration at pH ~ 1 .

red shifted (325–327 nm). The emission intensity is increased in both solutions. The above result indicates that HMB molecule is entrapped in the α -CD to form HMB; α -CD inclusion complex. An increase in the fluorescence intensity for the formation of an inclusion complex was observed earlier¹¹. The association constant for the formation of an inclusion complex has been determined by analyzing the changes in the intensities of absorption and fluorescence maxima with the α -CD concentration.

The association constant (k) and stoichiometric ratios of the inclusion complex of HMB with α -CD can be determined by using the Benesi-Hildebrand¹² relation. The k values were obtained from the slope and intercept of the plots. Fig. 2 depicts a plot of $1/A - A_0$ as a function of $1/[\alpha\text{-CD}]$ and Fig. 3 shows the plot of $1/I - I_0$ as a function of $1/[\alpha\text{-CD}]$ for HMB molecule. Good linear correlations were obtained confirming the formation of a 1 : 1 inclusion complex.

Fig. 2. Benesi-Hildebrand plot of $1/A - A_0$ versus $1/[\alpha\text{-CD}]$ for the complexation of HMB with α -CD.

Vanillic Acid

Fig. 3. Benesi-Hildebrand plot of $1/I - I_0$ versus $1/[\alpha\text{-CD}]$ for the complexation of HMB with α -CD.

Both in the absorption and fluorescence, the blue shift in pH ~ 1 and red shift in pH ~ 7 suggests selective inclusion is formed between HMB and α -CD. The formation constants are very sensitive to change of pH values, which supported the selective inclusion associated with the HMB (neutral, anion) species. Of the two species, we should note that α -CD can readily include the neutral species than the anionic species, because the neutral species is more hydrophobic than the anion. This orientation for the HMB molecule in the α -CD cavity is easy, because the α -CD cavity favours the neutral form of the benzoic acid derivatives^{13,14}. The higher formation constants in pH ~ 7 implies that the $-\text{COOH}$ group present in the interior of the α -CD cavity than the carboxylic anion. It is well known that substituents of aromatic rings capable of H-bonding can find the $-\text{OH}$ groups of the α -CD edges. The energy involved in such H-bond-

ing interactions is responsible for the higher binding constants, when compared to those of the unsubstituted molecules. At pH ~ 7 , the acid HMB will be anchored to the α -CD by the $-\text{COO}^-$ group a factor that confer stability to the inclusion complex. The spectral red shifts of HMB absorption and fluorescence at pH ~ 7 in α -CD medium is clearly established that HMB molecule is fully entrapped in the α -CD cavity. The difference in spectral change of HMB with addition of α -CD in pH ~ 1 compared to pH ~ 7 suggest that the structural geometry of HMB : α -CD inclusion complex are different in terms of orientation of guest molecule. It is well known that in α -CD solution, hydrophobicity is the driving force for encapsulation of the molecule inside the cavity and naturally the hydrophobic part would like to go inside the deep core ($-\text{OH}$) of the non-polar cavity and the $-\text{COOH}/\text{COO}^-$ group will be in the upper part of the α -CD cavity.

Considering the above results, the possible inclusion mechanism is proposed as follows : Naturally two different types of inclusion complex formation between HMB and α -CD is possible. One is with the carboxyl group captured (type-I) and the other is $-\text{OCH}_3$ and $-\text{OH}$ groups captured (type-II) in the α -CD cavity. In type-I arrangement, the carboxyl group of HMB is deeply entrapped in the α -CD cavity and in type-II arrangement $-\text{OCH}_3$ and $-\text{OH}$ groups of HMB is directly entrapped in the α -CD cavity. It is already reported that when the $-\text{OH}$ group is entrapped in the α -CD cavity in α -CD medium, the anions are blue shifted than aqueous medium¹⁵. These features indicate that in Scheme 1, type-II complex is favoured

Type-I

Type-II

Scheme 1. Inclusion complex of HMB with α -CD.

than type-I. This is further supported by using semiempirical AMI method. The internal diameter of the α -CD is approximately 5.3 Å and its height is 7.9 Å. To determine the dimensions of HMB geometry, the ground state was optimized by using AMI method (Scheme 1). The vertical distance between H_1 and H_6 , the horizontal distance between H_4 and H_7 and the length between $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{COOH}$ groups in HMB are lower than α -CD.

Microscopic morphological observation :

We observed powdered form of HMB and α -CD by scanning electron microscope. Then we also observed powdered form of inclusion complex (Fig. 4). Pictures clearly elucidated the difference of powder of each other. α -CD shows sheated structure, HMB shows stick structure and the complex structure is different from α -CD and HMB. Modification of crystals and powder can be assumed as a proof of the formation of new inclusion complex.

Conclusion :

Based on the above discussions the following conclusions can be drawn :

- (i) HMB forms 1 : 1 complex with α -CD.
- (ii) Both absorption and emission spectrum is slightly blue shifted in pH ~ 1 , but it is slightly red shifted in pH ~ 7 .
- (iii) The unusual blue shift in $-\text{OH}$ anion conforms that $-\text{OH}$ group is deeply entrapped in the α -CD cavity than $-\text{COOH}$.
- (iv) SEM and AMI studies supported the formation of inclusion complex.

HMB bond distance in Å

H_1-H_6	$= 7.554$	O_1-H_6	$= 6.936$	O_1-O_4	$= 6.415$
H_1-H_4	$= 7.300$	O_2-O_4	$= 6.490$	H_1-H_5	$= 5.970$
H_2-H_8	$= 4.333$	O_3-H_7	$= 4.552$		
H_4-H_7	$= 6.525$	O_2-H_6	$= 6.984$		

Fig. 4. Scanning electron microscope photographs (Pt. coated) of (a) α -CD, (b) HMB, (c) HMB : α -CD complex.

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